

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON

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ABSTRACT

Physical Culture and sport is an independent type of human activity and its importance in the development of society is very great. They significantly affect social production, the development of social relations, the formation of a person as an individual. Physical education is a pedagogical process aimed at the formation of a healthy, harmonious, socially active generation. Of particular importance is the consistent development of a lifestyle in which Physical Culture and sports are factors of the formation of a comprehensively and comprehensively developed personality. In this article, opinions and opinions are made about the importance of physical education in the formation of psychological health of a person.

Currently, physical education and sports are very popular. Articles devoted to sports, books are written, films dedicated to it, sociologists, doctors, historians, teachers and other specialists pay attention to the study of its problems. All this reflects not only the reputation of fashion, but also the position that physical culture and sports occupy in modern society. Physical education solves the problems of strengthening health, comprehensively developing physical and spiritual forces, increasing working capacity, creative longevity and life expectancy of busy people in all spheres of activity. In the process of physical education, the morphological and functional improvement of the human body, the development of physical qualities, the formation of motor

skills, special cognitive systems and their use in public practice and in everyday life are carried out. Physical exercises affect labor productivity, they contribute to the high creative activity of people engaged in mental labor. Regular training with certain sports and physical exercises, the correct use of them in the training mode will help to increase the mental abilities of students, improve a number of necessary qualities - depth of thinking, combinatorial abilities, operational, visual and auditory memory, sensory reactions. Physical education and sports are an important factor in reducing the level of diseases and injuries in the workplace.

Physical education and sports are necessary not only for people, but also for those whose profession requires special

physical exertion or special mental exertion, because modern living conditions (both in production and in everyday life) lead to an inevitable decrease in physical exertion.¹ A decrease in motor activity, in turn, leads to a decrease in the flexibility of the body, which is accompanied by a decrease in mental and physical ability to work, as well as a decrease in the resistance of the human body to diseases.

Physical Culture and sports have great opportunities to educate a comprehensively developed personality. In the process of training, moral, rational, labor and aesthetic education are carried out. At the same time, the influence of Physical Culture and sports on a person is very specific and cannot be overemphasized in other ways.

Systematic physical training and sports play an important role in improving mental performance. For example, the development of modern educational programs for university students is associated with an important psychic load. A high level of physical training is one of the important factors that contributes to the stagnation of mental activity throughout the school year. In the system "body condition - optimal physical activity - mental working capacity", it was found that the last connection is directly related to the first two. It was also noted that by the end of the school year, such indicators as the

¹ Pedagogy: pedagogical theories, systems, technologies: Proc. spend for students / S.A. Smirnov and others-M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 20079. - 544 p.

number of attention, memory and mental operations of poorly trained students have significantly decreased. Maintaining mental disability during this period is to ensure the continuity of physical exercise and sports, taking into account the physical condition of each student, and to regulate the training loads in this regard, as well as to ensure a positive emotional environment in the classroom.

A person who is engaged in sports is constantly acquainted with the symbols of beauties. Under the influence of exercise, body forms develop harmoniously, movements and movements become more subtle, energetic, beautiful. Many people are engaged in sports, follow only specific practical goals - improving health, setting a record, etc.² In many ways, they will be able to get aesthetic pleasure from the lessons, constantly monitor the beauty and create it in the form of perfect beauty movements with the elegance of having your own body. The link between physical education and sports and aesthetic education is effective, because it allows not only to create a beautiful external image, but also to influence the moral and willpower qualities, the aesthetics of actions and behavior in modern society.

In the theory and practice of physical education, there are different groups and types of prints: the general principles of the system of physical education, the stylistic principles that characterize the individual types of physical education (for example, sports

² Branet C. Cretty. Psychology in modern sport.- M.: Physical education and sports, 2005.- It's 432.p

training).³ They are closely related to each other and form a system of single prints. Everyone should strive to be useful to their country and society. But this can only be done by people with all-round developed spiritual and physical powers. But they can arise under the influence of certain social conditions of life, among which physical education occupies a special place.

The spiritual world of man develops externally and, first of all, under the influence of the social environment, and also because of the active efforts of man to change the environment and himself. In the process of physical education - due to the physical and spiritual development of a person, there are great opportunities for the realization of the functions of intellectual moral and aesthetic education.

The requirements for general physical training are based on one of the Basic Laws of human development - the inextricability of systems and organs. The physical training is an integral foundation of any type of activity and serves as an inexhaustible source of moral and physical strength of a person. Some scientists use the basic functions of Physical Culture and sports in the removal of the rigidity of modern life. But there is another point of view - physical education was created to train people who work effectively and protect their homeland from the assassination of enemies. There is an opinion that the practical importance of physical education consists only in the development of motor skills necessary in

³ Basova N.V. Pedagogy and practical psychology. - Rostov n/ A: "Phoenix", 2004.- The 416.p

life. If a skill is applied, which is formed as a result of training with this or that type of exercise, that is. it can be transferred to a working or military environment, then such physical education is associated with life. The goal is that a person who comes to production or the army will be able to master the techniques of any business in a short time. It is desirable that only a strong, enthusiastic and developed person quickly mastered a new job, new technologies.

Medical supervision of students is required for all organizations engaged in physical education. However, medical observation should not be limited to reporting only about the changes that occur in the human body. In addition to special pedagogical observation indicators, medical observation data are objects, with the help of which it is possible to assess the positive or negative impact of physical exercises, to change and improve the methods of physical education. A print of the fact that the Daily creative team of the doctor, teacher and practitioner is directed to the improvement of the internal system of physical education.⁴ If the therapist senses a deterioration in health, and the doctor confirms this through analysis, he should move away from intensive sports and be satisfied with physical exercise as a therapeutic tool. The doctor and the teacher are obliged to know in advance the possible long-term consequences of these classes on the basis of accounting on the basis of accounting for changes in the body

⁴ Wolfov B.3., Ivanov V.D. The basics of pedagogy in lectures, situations, primary sources: textbook. - M.: Urao publishing house, 2006.- The 288p.

involved in the performance of the exercises.

Conclusion. No one can compare it with the ever-changing power of Physical Culture and sports. This power makes the person who complains of fatigue-hard, painful-healthy, stubborn, sluggish, fast, weak, strong. Good physical training allows you to quickly learn new complex production professions; this has also become one of the decisive factors in the training of pilots, cosmonauts and servicemen. Physical Culture and sport contribute to the development of mental processes-attention, clarity of perception, memory, reproduction, imagination,

thinking, improvement of mental activity. Healthy, hardened, physical well-developed boys and girls, as a rule, take good educational materials, are less tired at school lessons, do not leave lessons because of colds. Physical education is also the most important means of shaping an individual as a person. Physical exercises allow you to influence consciousness, willpower, moral character, character traits of boys and girls in many ways. They not only bring about significant biological changes in the body, but in many ways determine the development of morals, habits, tastes and other aspects that characterize the spiritual world of man.

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